

Morphology and local current mapping of wrinkled reduced graphene oxide

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Abstract

The heterogeneous electronic structure of reduced graphene oxide (rGO) due to the presence of sp^2 and sp^3 bonding make it a promising candidate for many applications including energy storage. However, in order to utilize the material for applications it is essential to understand the nanoscale behavior of the rGO, especially how wrinkling affect the structural and electronic properties. Here, we use a conducting atomic force microscopy (CAFM) to correlate the structural and electrical characteristics of rGO. The rGO wrinkles (~ 110 nm in width and ~ 8 nm in height) show larger electrical conductance (25 pA) than the other part of rGO sheets (inset Fig.1b). I-V spectroscopy measurement (Fig.1b) further demonstrates that the wrinkles have low turn-on voltage (7.4 V), indicating the electrical conduction occurs through inter-layer tunneling mechanism, which is in agreement with recent predictions [1]. These results emphasize the morphology and electronic properties of wrinkled rGO, which will be useful for graphene based electronic devices.

Figure 1. Representative AFM topographic image of rGO (a) and current-voltage measurement of rGO at different regions marked in CAFM image (inset fig.b).

Keywords: Graphene-oxide, current domains, wrinkles and inter-layers tunneling.

Reference:

1. W. Zhu et al, Nano Lett. 2012, 12, 3431 – 3436.